

Supporting Information: Pressure-Controlled Nanopipette Sensing in the Asymmetric-Conductivity Configuration

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1 Modulation of the Conductivity by Altering the Viscosity with Glycerol

Figure S1: A) Current-potential curves for the asymmetric-conductivity configuration where the conductivity is modulated by viscosity. All concentrations are 50 mM KCl with varying amounts of glycerol in the bulk solution. B) Current-potential curve for pure aqueous solution before and after changing the bulk concentration, showing that the strategy of subsequently changing the bulk concentration is valid.

2 Calculation of Current Hysteresis

Current hysteresis is calculated as the forward sweep current subtracted from the backwards sweep current as defined in Figure S1 and Equation S1 and S2:

$$R_{\text{hyst,negative potentials}} = i_2(E) - i_1(E)$$

Equation S1

$$R_{\text{hyst,positive potentials}} = i_4(E) - i_3(E)$$

Equation S2

The potential-time waveform used for nanopipette measurements in bulk is shown in Figure S1A and the resulting current-potential plot in Figure S1B. Note that when calculating the current hysteresis current, the current from the forward and reverse sweep are evaluated at the same potential (shown by arrows in Figure S1B). Because the currents at negative potentials are negative, a lowered current magnitude with time corresponds to a negative current hysteresis. The resulting hysteresis current is shown in the main manuscript in Figure 2C.

Figure S2: A) Potential-time waveform for nanopipette experiments in bulk B) Experimental current-potential curve showing clear hysteresis. Back arrows connect the 2 data points that are used in the calculation of hysteresis current at each potential.

3 Multiple Scans at the Same Scan Rate During Scan Rate Analysis

Figure S3: Three consecutive current-potentials curves in the asymmetric conductivity configuration ($R_{dil} = 3$, and scan rate = 0.5 V/s), demonstrating no drift in the data for a given scan rate.

4 Effect of Pipette Surface Charge on Ion Current Rectification and Current Hysteresis

Figure S4: A) current-potential curves before (top) and after (bottom) poly-L-lysine (PLL) modification. Conditions: $R_{dil} = 3$, and scan rate = 4 V/s. The expected curves from evaluating the resistance at 0 V is shown in dashed grey lines for comparison. B) Current hysteresis-potential curves from the data from (A). C) Curves before and after modification with 400 mbar of external pressure applied to show that the resistive behavior is the same before and after treatment, demonstrating the there was no substantial change in pipette size.

5 Definition of Nanopipette Inner Cone Half Angle

Figure S5: Geometrical definition of the nanopipette inner cone half angle.

6 Evaluation of Pipette Size by Comparison to Simulations

Figure S6: Simulated current-potential curves for different pipette sizes, compared to the experimental curve (blue line). The scan rate was 4 V/s, and the bulk and pipette electrolyte were 50 mM and 150 mM KCl, respectively.

7 Current Hysteresis in Simulated Data

Figure S7: A) Simulated current-potential curves for different scan rates. B) Hysteresis-potential curves calculated from simulated current-potential curves from (A). The pipette radius was 250 nm, and the bulk and pipette electrolyte were 50 mM and 150 mM KCl, respectively.

8 Effect of Pipette Potential on the Current Peak Magnitude

Figure S8: Effect of pipette potential on the normalized current peaks observed over a silicon wafer in the asymmetric-conductivity configuration for an approach rate of 250 nm/s and a pipette concentration of 150 mM.

9 Glycerol Addition to Bulk for Constant Electrolyte Concentration

Figure S9: Approach curves for different pipette potentials and bulk solutions with a pipette solution of 50 mM KCl in 10% glycerol. A) 50 mM KCl. B) 50 mM KCl in 10% glycerol. C) 50 mM KCl in 25% glycerol. D) 50 mM KCl in 50% glycerol. Approach rate was 250 nm/s.

10 Effect of Pipette Charge on Current Hysteresis Peaks

Figure S10: Max normalized current versus potential for approach curve experiments over a silicon wafer for different pipette charges, negative (unmodified) and positive (poly-L-lysine (PLL) modified). Approach rate was 250 nm/s, R_{dil} was 3 and the pipette concentration was 150 mM KCl.

11 Effect of Approach Parameters on Current Hysteresis Peaks

Figure S11: Approach curves for different pipette potentials (A/B), approach setpoints (C/D) and approach rate (E/F) for $R_{dil} = 3$ and pipette concentration of 150 mM KCl. The pipette potential was -100 mV and the approach rate was 250 nm/s unless otherwise specified.

12 Fibrinogen Patterning

Figure S12: Scheme illustrating the fibrinogen patterning method (described in detail in the experimental section).

13 Hysteresis Mapping of Circular Fibrinogen Patterns

Figure S13: Maximum normalized current map of circular fibrinogen patterns by evaluating the maximum current in the retract curve. Conditions: R_{dil} was 5, pipette potential was -250 mV and approach/retract rate was $4 \mu\text{m/s}$.

14 Tuning the Hysteresis for Approach Curves Using Externally Applied Pressure

Figure S14: Approach-retract curves for varying applied pressures. Conditions: R_{dil} was 5, pipette concentration was 150 mM KCl, potential was -250 mV, and approach/retract rate was 250 nm/s.

15 Additional Information on Simulations with Externally Applied Pressure

Figure S15: A) v across the nanopipette aperture for R_{dil} 5 at 0 V for externally applied pressure. B) v_{mean} at different potentials for different pressures. C) $(C_{K^+, mean} + C_{Cl^-, mean}) / 2$ across the nanopipette aperture during a simulated i - E sweep.

16 Bulk Behavior of Nanopipette Used for Constant-Current Imaging

Figure S16: A) Current evaluated at -100 mV versus applied pressure. B) R_{rect} evaluated versus pressure. Conditions: $R_{\text{dil}} = 3$, pipette concentration of 150 mM KCl, scan rate of 4 V/s, and pipette radius of approximately 50 nm (nanopipette used for constant-current imaging).

17 Noise Properties in the Asymmetric-Conductivity Configuration

Figure S17: A-B,D-E) Normalized current-time traces for constant potentials (-100 and +100 mV) with pressures pulses starting from 0 mbar (2 min each). Conditions: pipette concentration was 150 mM KCl and the pipette radius was approximately 250 nm. C,F) Evaluated root-mean-square error (RMSE) as a function of pressure.

18 Boundary Conditions for Finite-Element Simulations

Boundary conditions used here are described in Table S1 and Figure S17. Ion diffusion coefficients for K^+ and Cl^- were taken from the CRC Handbook, which are $1.957^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $2.032^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. The equations are solved using COMSOL Multiphysics (version 6.1) and further details can be found in the model report included as Supporting Information 2.

Boundary	Poisson	Nernst-Planck	Navier-Stokes
B1	Pipette potential	150 mM K^+ 150 mM Cl^-	Applied pressure
B2	Pipette wall surface charge density (-5 mC m^{-2})	No flux	No slip
B3	No charge	No flux	No slip
B4	Ground (0 V)	Bulk concentration	Zero pressure
B5	No charge	Not solved	Not solved

Table S1: Description of boundary conditions used in simulations.

Figure S17: Schematic of the axis-symmetric geometry used in simulations. B1 and B4 represent the semi-infinite bulk of the pipette and the bath, respectively. B2 represents the nanopipette walls. B3 represents the solution surface.